

Branding as a Part of Tourist Destination Development

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ABSTRACT

Destination branding is of special importance to the development of tourism in accordance with the requirements of tourist demand. The brand builds loyalty and reduces the risk associated with the intangibility of tourism products. In addition to the growth of tourist demand, the number of protected areas within which tourism is developing in accordance with the prescribed protection system is also increasing. The objectives of the analysis in the paper are: importance of tourist destinations and protected areas as brands; opportunities for tourism development in protected areas; and elements of branding in the tourist region of Western Serbia.

1. Introduction

There are different theoretical approaches to brand and branding, but its essence is unchanged. “The brand is not a logo. The brand is not an identity. The brand is not a product. The brand is the inner feeling of consumers about a product, service or company” (Neumeier, 2008). The brand is, also, described as “a unique identifier, a symbol, a form name, or a combination thereof that marks the product of a particular manufacturer or store in order to distinguish between that product and other similar products, i.e. products of other enterprises. We distinguish manufacturer and trademark. If the legal registration of a brand is made, the trademark is also used.” (Aćimović et al., 2006)

Certain approaches make the difference between the brand and the mark. A mark is a recognizable name, a sign, a symbol, or a combination thereof that identifies the products or services of an enterprise, while the brand is a recognizable identity that distinguishes a relevant and long-term promise of value that is associated with the product, service or organization and indicates a source of promise (Ward et al., 1999). A very important element of the brand is related to building brand - the elements of brand building should be such that they can be easily remembered (Keller, 2003). Building a brand can have multiple perspectives, so an external perspective refers to finding a way that gives members of the target segment greater value and meaning. The time perspective refers to the development of the brand and the management of the brand over a long period of time (Kotler & Keller, 2012).

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The land brand is defined as “a unique, multidimensional mix of elements that build a nation differentiated from others based on cultural specificity” (Dinnie, 2008: 15). The country’s branding represents its promotion, i.e. “public diplomacy closely linked to the process of national branding and representing the country in the best way” (Anholt, 2007: 14). It is therefore important that the state creates, promotes, protects and monitors the brand of a country (Rawson, 2007: 213). National branding is a complex process whose main goal is to differentiate the country from other countries in the international environment and position it according to its specificities in order to strengthen the image from the political, economic, social, historical and cultural aspects. The state is the one who needs to protect and oversee the brand of a country, but the fact that the population of the country is the main bearer of the branding process must certainly be taken into account.

The attractiveness of the land is measured using an algorithm that represents an equation composed of four key variables (Bloom Consulting Country Brand Ranking, 2017):

1) Economic impact of tourism – the variable consists of two sizes: economic revenues of tourism and economic growth of tourism. The 2010-2014 average places Europe again as the continent with the largest touristic revenue. In terms of growth, Asia continues to show strong growth in 2014.

2) On-line search demand (OSD) – a measurement system used to estimate global on-line searches specifically for tourism. Europe is this year’s most searched continent by international tourists worldwide, overtaking Asia compared to the previous ranking edition. Asia now comes in second, followed closely by the Americas.

3) The accuracy of the strategy implemented by the national tourism organization – the accuracy is measured through the value that each “brand tag” produces for the country. If the country uses the most sought-after and most valuable brand tags, its rating increases and vice versa. In this way, it is possible to conclude how many branded tags contribute to the brand of the country which are branded tags that were promoted but did not benefit as well as what are branded tags that were not used and could have positive impact. Europe maintains its leadership position in terms of CBS rating compared to last year’s ranking while Americas scales up putting more countries with AA and A ratings. New African entries in the ranking cope with the “Poor” rating classification.

4) Visibility and positioning in the digital world – the variable is given by the official website of the national tourist organization as well as the activities of the country in the online communities of Facebook and Twitter. Facebook continues to be the platform with most users, followed by Twitter and Instagram. Since last year, Europe takes over the Americas on Facebook and increases its Instagram performance compared to Oceania.

Tourist destination branding is a concept that started developing in the late XX century and integrates all the features of the destination into a single whole, which expresses a unique identity (Tsaur et al., 2016). The combination of food,

culture and tourism has become an emerging tourism product called gastronomy, regarded as a vehicle for regional, local and sustainable development of a particular destination. Gastronomy is significant because of its ethical and sustainable values that are based on local food, culture, traditions, lifestyles, practices that not only allure the visitors but also at the same time promote the destination marketing (Mohanty et al., 2020).

2. Literature Review

Place branding is defined as the practice of applying brand strategy and other marketing techniques and disciplines to the economic, political and cultural development of cities, regions and countries (Ashworth & Kavaratzis, 2009). The implementation of marketing methodology, or at least of marketing techniques that were easy to adapt and use in the practice of city governance, has been mirrored by the increasing interest of academics from various fields, who believe that the principles of marketing are, with the necessary modifications, applicable to cities and their operational environment (Kavaratzis, 2004).

The use of branding concepts in tourism and the creation of a brand are also influenced by own products or services that are known on regional, national, or global scale. Therefore, any branding of a city or destination must take into account the perception and image of local production brands. Marketing experts must offer experience through visiting a destination and branding not just through the name, logo and sign. Each or most destinations have hotels, congress facilities, unique cultural heritage, natural or artistic attractions, entertainment or other forms of touristic content that seek to increase the value of the destination brand. For a tourist destination, it is important to recognize the tourist product. The reason is the usual behaviour of tourists who choose a tourist destination according to its popularity or recognition. The destination brand expresses its location, activities and content within its boundaries.

The brand of the tourist destination is influenced by a positive image that emphasizes the specificity of a country both in terms of tourist attractions, natural beauties, as well as, in terms of rich culture and history of the country and hospitality. The branding of the destination implies: "the formation of a clear, recognizable, ambitious, but also a real brand position, positioning a brand based on values, attitudes, behaviour and characteristics of the population, formulating a clear strategy for branding a destination and its main points with emphasis on skills, resources and abilities, effective offers for target groups, conducting successful communication with key stakeholders, and ensuring the integrity and consistency of communications that are conducted through various media" (Divandari et al., 2014: 76).

In order to build a destination brand, it is necessary for the branding process to go through several phases (Morgan et al., 2004). The first phase in the process of building the brand of destination is the establishment of the basic value and brand by being sustainable and striking for potential tourists. After the end of market research,

analysis and strategic recommendations, the brand identity (colors, brand mark, photos) is being developed. All components of the brand identity should be linked so as to make an inseparable entity that is conceived. The destination brand should create an emotional attachment to the destination by being credible, transmitting powerful ideas and differentiated. Therefore, there are several phases within which the destination brand is created (Table 1).

Table 1. Phases of the brand destination design

Phase 1	Market research, analysis and strategic recommendations
Phase 2	Identity brand development
Phase 3	Introduction and branding-vision transfer
Phase 4	Implementation of the brand
Phase 5	Monitoring, evaluation (evaluation) and review (control)

Source: Morgan et al. (2004: 69)

2.1. Tourism development and protected areas

Protected areas are areas characterized by significant geological, biological, ecosystem and/or landscape diversity which is why they are declared protected areas of general interest by the protection act. Protected areas represent protected natural assets, in addition to protected species and mobile protected natural documents.

The protected area of Category I is an area of international, national or extraordinary significance and is located on the whole territory in the territory of two or more units of local self-government. Area of Category II relates to a protected area of a provincial, regional or high importance. Protected areas of Category III are of local importance and are proclaimed by the local self-government.

Protected areas can be defined in seven different categories or species: National Park, Nature Park, Exceptional Features Area, General and Special Nature Reserve, Nature Monument and Protected Habitat. According to the statistical data of the United Nations List of Protected Areas by 2003, 102.102 areas have been protected, covering 18.763.407 km². The number of protected areas has increased from 9.214 in 1962 to 102.102 areas. The protected areas increased by 7.9 times, from 2.4 million km² to 18.8 million km² (Table 2 and Fig. 1).

Table 2. Protected areas and their surface

Year	Number of protected areas	Surface (million km ²)
1962	9.214	2.4
1972	16.394	4.1
1982	27.794	8.8
1992	48.388	12.3
2003	102.102	18.8

Source: UN (2003)

Fig. 2. Increase in the number of protected areas

Source: UN (2003)

Protected spaces are ranked in six categories according to IUCN regulations. Within this category system, they vary according to the level of human activity, and Category I has minimal human involvement and Category VI is the highest (Table 3).

Table 3. Categories of protected areas according to IUCN

IUCN Category	Category
Category Ia	Strict nature reserve
Category Ib	Wilderness area
Category II	National park
Category III	Natural monument or feature
Category IV	Habitat/species management area
Category V	Protected landscape/seascape
Category VI	Protected area with sustainable use of natural resources

Source: UN (2003)

Depending on the value and importance, the protected area is classified in Category I, II or III. Category I refers to a protected area of international, national, or exceptional importance. It is mostly a national park, a strict and special reserve, a habitat, a natural good that is protected on the basis of international acts or is of international significance, a landscape of exceptional qualities in which the cultural property of extraordinary significance is located, as well as, a nature park that is on the whole surface territories of two or more units of local self-government. Category II refers to the protected area of the provincial/regional, or of great importance. It is mostly a habitat and a landscape of exceptional features in which cultural property is not of great importance, if their entire area is in the territory of the autonomous province, as well as, a nature park located on the territory of two or more units of local self-government in the territory of the autonomous province. Category III refers to a protected area of local significance. This can most often be a nature park, a monument of nature and an area of exceptional features in which cultural property is of no great relevance, and which is the whole area on the territory of the local self-government unit.

The protection regime is a set of measures and conditions that determine the manner and degree of protection, use, regulation and improvement of a protected natural asset. In the National Park, I, II, and III degree protection regimes are established in accordance with the law. From the aspect of protection there are differences between the regions. The largest percentage of protected areas was in Antarctic (81% with predominant protection Category 1a). In Europe, this percentage is 46.1 and the predominant category of protection is from Category V (Table 4).

Table 4. Protected areas in the world according to UN List of Protected Areas

IUCN Category	Number of protected areas (ZP)	% of total ZP	Area (km ²)	% of total ZP
Category Ia	4.731	4.6	1.033.888	5.5
Category Ib	1.302	1.3	1.015.512	5.4
Category II	3.881	3.8	4.413.142	23.6
Category III	19.833	19.4	275.432	1.5
Category IV	27.641	27.1	3.022.515	16.1
Category V	6.555	6.4	1.056.008	5.6
Category VI	4.123	4.0	4.377.091	23.3
Without IUCN category	34.036	33.4	3.569.820	19.0
Total	102.102	100.0	18.763.407	100.00

Source: UN (2003)

The World Tourism Organization of the United Nations (UNWTO) estimated that international tourist arrivals exceeded 1.24 billion in 2016, generated over US\$ 1.22 trillion in international tourism receipts, and contributed 10% of the world's GDP (UNWTO, 2017). Growing tourist visibility, also, creates certain environmental pressures. The impact of tourism on biodiversity and its conservation was dealt with in a number of works (McCool & Moisey, 2008; Buckley, 2012; Hvenegaard et al., 2012).

Tourism in protected areas contribute to the conservation of nature (environmental value) and generate economic benefits. Destination managers in its development should respect the following guidelines: development is harmonized with the context of the protected area, appreciates the experience of visitors, the development of the ethics of protecting the area of the visitor and respects the special needs of the local community (Leung et al., 2018).

The effects of tourism development can be positive and negative, especially from the aspect of the development of protected areas. Positive effects are reflected in (Leung et al., 2014):

- Clearly identifying and linking biodiversity benefits which can support better monitoring and evaluation;
- Proactively engaging tourism stakeholders in local legislation and the development of policy frameworks;

- Increasing the number of visitors, the length of stay and concession opportunities can increase economic opportunities for local employment;
- A deeper affinity for conserving the protected area;
- Ensuring revenue from tourism goes back into paying for conservation management and mitigating any negative tourism impacts in the area.

Visits to protected areas indicate that visits to these areas have dropped (Canada, Japan and the United States) due to the reduction of national support and funding. Compared to 1994 and 2012, the number of visitors to national parks in Canada has decreased by 28.7% which could have contributed to the government's 2012 decision to cut budgets and staff to national parks.

Protected area managers are struggling with a variety of challenges including climate change, illegal wildlife trade, inadequate infrastructure, and competitive interests for natural resources. However, with appropriate management systems, an increase in the number of visitors can bring much needed income from input fees, guides, accommodation and concessions which can be invested in conservation activities.

It is important to identify and evaluate the real costs and impacts of tourism in protected areas, in order to clearly understand the opportunities and challenges associated with the development of tourism in these areas.

With expectations that international travel will increase, managers of protected areas should mitigate any negative impacts as a result of increased visits, but also recognize new opportunities arising from this potential demand that can provide income for preservation and local economies. Partnerships with local communities, private companies and the government have an important role to play to help balance the provision of long-term support for these critical areas.

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic negatively affects the development of the tourism industry. The rapid spread of COVID-19 has significantly affected global tourism, which has suffered serious consequences especially attractive tourist destinations, such as France, Italy and Spain (Ruiz Estrada et al., 2020). COVID-19 would have severe consequences on the global tourism industry by reducing travel by 25% in 2020 and generating a loss of 50 million jobs that would require at least ten months for this industry to recover (Folinas & Metaxas, 2020).

2.2. Protected areas in Republic of Serbia

The following forms are included in the regime of protected areas in Serbia: national parks, strict nature reserves, special nature reserves, natural monuments, protected habitats, areas of exceptional features and nature parks. National parks are areas with a large number of diverse ecosystems of national importance that have special landscape features and cultural heritage in which people can live in harmony with nature. Strict nature reserves are areas in which unchanged natural features contain representative natural ecosystems that represent areas in which unaltered nature is preserved, genetic funds, sustainable ecological balance. Special nature reserves are areas in which the state of nature has not changed or slightly changed,

which are important due to their uniqueness, rarity or representativeness, and which are at the same time habitats of endangered wild plant and animal species. Natural monuments are less unaltered or partially altered natural areas or wholes, objects or phenomena that are clearly physically expressed, recognizable and unique. Protected habitats are areas that include one or more types of natural habitats that are important for the conservation of individual or multiple populations of wild species and their communities. Landscapes of exceptional features are areas that have a recognizable and special appearance with significant biological-ecological, aesthetic and cultural-historical values. Nature parks are areas of well-preserved natural properties of water, air and soil without major degradation processes.

Out of a total of 463 protected assets with an area of 522 thousand hectares, national parks participate in the total area with 30.45%, nature parks with 41.32%, special nature reserves 16.74% while other forms of protection, 429 of them occupy 11.49 % of the total area of protected areas (Table 5).

Table 5. Protected natural assets in Serbia

No.	Protected areas	Serbia	
		Number	Surface (ha)
1	National parks	5	158.986,36
2	Nature parks	12	215.760,57
3	Regional nature parks	4	361,86
4	Landscapes of exceptional qualities	12	33.406,80
5	Landscapes of special natural beauty	4	12.105,63
6	Forest Park	1	19,65
7	Strict nature reserves	42	2.207,28
8	Strict nature reserves	4	60,49
9	General nature reserve	17	87.410,14
10	Monuments of nature	327	7.681,00
11	Memorial natural monuments	19	2.394,67
12	Spaces in the vicinity of immovable cultural property	16	1.725,55
13	Strictly protected species	1681	
14	Protected species	821	
	In total	463	522.120

Source: Strategy for biological diversity of the Republic of Serbia for 2011-2018²; State Enterprise "Srbijašume"³

Zlatibor Region is located in Southeast Europe and occupies the southwestern part of the Republic of Serbia. In the Zlatibor area, great potentials for the development of tourism in mountain destinations have been noticed. Within the Zlatibor area, from the aspect of tourism development, the tourist region of Western Serbia is defined, which includes several areas that are protected by different levels

² https://transformator.bos.rs/uploads/library1501069408_strategija-bioloske-raznovrsnosti-2011-2018.pdf

³ <https://srbijasume.rs/en/>

of protection (NP Tara area, Zlatibor Nature Park and others). Zlatibor, Tara, Zlatar and Mokra Gora are also tourist destinations. According to the data of the Republic Bureau of Statistics, from January to October 2010, 332,762 foreigners stayed in mountainous places in Serbia, who realized a total of 1,309,032 overnight stays during that time. Based on the recorded number of overnight stays, the mountain centers are in the second place of visit, after the spa places. The highest number of domestic tourists was 295,460, while 77,302 foreigners were vacationing in the mountains of Serbia, which is seven percent more than in the same period last year. Tourism on Zlatibor and Zlatar began to develop more intensively in the late seventies and early eighties of the twentieth century. The plans that were created at that time included the construction of large receptive facilities of the middle value category. The goal was to enable wintering, summer and climate treatment and rehabilitation for a larger number, mostly domestic tourists.

The general goal of tourism development is to achieve sustainable tourism development according to EU standards while increasing the competitiveness of the tourist offer through the development of several types of tourism: mountain, excursion-weekend, transit (road and river), sports-recreational, climate, events, rural, cultural, hunting, with a simultaneous increase in the standard of living of the local population, especially those that are directly or indirectly related to the development of tourism. The importance of preserving the environment, the concept of development based on available natural resources, the awareness of the local population that wants to preserve indigenous values and the valorization of cultural and historical monuments and their protection for future generations are especially emphasized.

The development of tourism in the mountain destinations of the Zlatibor district should respect the general goal of tourism development with the realization of types of tourism that are in line with available resources. The most attractive should be educational and ecological types of tourism, primarily ornithological, harmonized with the regimes of protection of natural values and professionally supported and controlled by the guardians of protected areas. On the meanders of the Uvac River in the protection regime of the Ib degree, the priority is the arrangement of the planned lookout in the canyon and the habitat of the griffon vulture. The following contents are planned on lakes and rivers: water sports (rowing, sailing, etc.), sport fishing, rafting on the meanders of Uvac (in the protection regime of Ib degree of natural values), etc.

Traditional rural tourism is of year-round character with distinct peaks during the summer and winter tourist seasons. Priority is given to the development of rural tourism, new accommodation capacities and contents of the tourist offer in settlements in the zone with the protection regime of III degree and in the immediate vicinity of SRP Uvac.

Year-round health and rehabilitation tourism will take place at the existing locations of the air spa on Zlatar (prevention, treatment and rehabilitation of cardiovascular diseases), with the necessary modernization and adaptation of

accommodation facilities of the special hospital, as well as private rehabilitation centers (wellness) in villages with III degree protection regime around Zlatar Lake. For the needs of fishing tourism, it is necessary to arrange fishing trails in places where fishermen gather along the Uvac River.

Hunting and fishing tourism include control of the use of biological capacities and prevention of excessive hunting and fishing, control of poaching and time allowed for hunting/fishing of certain species. Accommodation for hunters and fishermen will be organized in rural settlements, hunting lodges and other commercial tourist facilities. In the area of mountain destinations, it is possible to encourage adventure tourism, which includes trips that are a personal challenge for the traveler, and whose main goal is to explore new experiences with a certain risk or controlled level of danger.

4. Results and Discussion

In parallel with the educational activities of public and private sector entities, it is necessary to launch a promotional campaign aimed at raising public awareness and better understanding of the local population about the importance, benefits and multiplicative effects of tourism development and quality value chain in tourism to Western Serbia. The basis of the offer of the destination Zlatibor-Zlatar are products of vacations and cruises, which already have a somewhat built tourist value chain and need to be marketed more strongly towards the emitting market.

Products for medium-term development are special interests for which, in addition to marketing, it is necessary to invest in elements of the tourist value chain (investments in general and tourist infrastructure are needed), events and culture (also, additional investments are needed in event design) and further invest in meeting space. Products of additional value are gastronomy, rural tourism, sports tourism and nautics, which although not the primary motive for coming to the tourist area give the emotional dimension of the stay (enjoy local specialties, in a rural setting, enjoy sports activities and sail the river/lake).

The issue of brand positioning and its development have their predetermined steps that must be implemented in order to deliver a highly professional tourism brand. The first step is to determine the strength and weakness of the brand of the tourist destination Western Serbia. Positioning a brand based on strengths and weaknesses (image) further means identifying the elements through the benefits and attributes that form the basis (core) of the destination.

Table 6. Strengths and weaknesses of the brand of Western Serbia tourist region

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Sources of resources for differentiation;▪ Sources for differentiation are very important to target groups;▪ The product portfolio is tailored to the target market;▪ The product portfolio is tailored to the target market;▪ The guests' experiences are positive;▪ Zlatibor has a positive connotation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ General image of the destination;▪ General condition of the infrastructure;▪ The popularity and image of the destination is low in the emitting markets.

Source: Strategic and Operational Tourism Plan of the Destination Zlatibor-Zlatar (2013)

Product tactics according to the Strategic and Operational Tourism Plan of the Destination Zlatibor-Zlatar (2013: 61-83):

1) We are all destinations

The essence is that every provider of direct or indirect tourist services understand that the overall satisfaction of tourists depends on all subjects. All direct and indirect factors in the offer of the tourist region of Western Serbia will become part of the integral value chain in tourism. In order to create a successful destination, this program includes a training/educational part intended for the entire destination of Western Serbia, especially focused on professionals in the tourism sector, as well as, members of other public and service services who indirectly contact tourists.

2) Identification of the visual identity of the destination Western Serbia

It is necessary to define one, maximum two visual solutions (brands) of the destination Western Serbia as a unique tourist product. Visual identity allows the destination to become recognizable and positioned in relation to competitors. In some cases, it is based on built-in attractions (as is the case with Big Ben, a symbol of London and England). A symbol can be a typical thing or phenomenon characteristic of the whole area (e.g. Dutch windmills, or Canadian maple, or Australian kangaroo), or it can be a historical element (such as the Hadrian's Wall), etc. The regional tourism organization, local governments, tourism companies, TOS, the ministry in charge of tourism should use this symbol in the context of promotion in every useful situation. The symbol should also be used as a trademark in the production of souvenirs and other authentic products for the destination.

3) Top 5 attractions of tourist destination Western Serbia

These attractions are the main products, around which additional services, contents and experiences can be developed. Expanding the offer on the basis of these attractions enables the creation of more complex tourist products, and satisfying different categories of tourists. The destination will be more successful in selling and delivering experiences if the integral tourist product is complex, which implies that it is composed of the most important 5 attacks, which are followed by attractions and second-class experiences.

4) Voluntary labeling system

Labeling aims to improve communication with tourists, through the development of a labeling system that allows the classification of tourist products and services within the destination according to the level of possession of certain characteristics and experiences. The system is based on the initial determination of the level in relation to which the existence of defined quality and specific attributes is measured. Some of the directions in which the system can go when creating labels as a guarantee of quality: eco labels for natural attractions; voluntary labeling of the quality of accommodation, regardless of the legal preconditions that must be met; introduction of standardization in ethno village category communications; labeling system for restaurants with local and traditional cuisine; a system of labeling local products that can be purchased at the market or directly from the host; marking capacities for sports and recreational facilities.

5) Tourist signalization

Three categories of tourist signage should be developed:

- promotional signage: attracts tourists to a particular resource or attraction;
- informative signaling: provides information about a resource or attraction;
- location signalization: shows the way to certain places and gives orientation on the spot.

Based on the products proposed by the Tourism Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2006-2015, as well as, the document "Business (Master) plan of the tourist destination Zlatibor-Zlatar", a portfolio of products to focus marketing efforts is defined (Zlatibor-Zlatar, 2013):

- Holidays, which as a product can be defined as holidays with the aim of enjoying and gaining new experiences in rest areas;
- Cruises, as one of the oldest concepts of travel, which is defined as movement through space with the aim of discovering and getting to know a large number of tourist attractions of a space;
- Of particular interest is a leisure activity that takes place in an unusual or wild environment;
- Events/culture are an important part of the marketing of most professionally run tourism destinations;
- Business/MICE can be defined as travel motivated by professional and business reasons, which includes activities such as problem solving, tasks, education and/ or attending certain MICE events;
- Gastronomy is the enjoyment of traditional local gastronomic specialties, as well as participation in the preparation, production and packaging of traditional dishes/drinks of the local population;
- Rural tourism can be defined as the travel of tourists with the purpose of staying in a rural/rural environment, as well as, participating in the daily traditional activities of the local population;
- Sports tourism is a form of travel conditioned primarily by the motives of engaging in certain sports activities;

- Nautics is a type of tourist product whose main purpose is to stay on the river through cruising, sailing or individual sailing on rivers or lakes.

Mountain destinations, both qualitatively and quantitatively, have a huge wealth of natural and anthropogenic tourist values that are insufficiently economically valorized. The dominant part of this area is Zlatibor, as the most visited mountain destination. Zlatibor district is the carrier of mountain tourism in Serbia with the mountains Zlatibor, Tara, Zlatar and Mokra Gora because these four mountains participate in visits to mountain places in Serbia with 46%, and only Zlatibor accounts for 27.83%; based on which it is concluded that every second tourist visits one of the mountains in the Zlatibor district, and every fourth visits Zlatibor.

The analysis in the paper shows that: the number of protected areas is growing, the protected areas are in different protection regimes, the development of tourism can take place in accordance with the protection regime, the tourist region is branded, the most visited destination in the tourist region is also a protected area, to develop a marketing strategy that contributes to brand development and that the marketing strategy contains key elements and directions of development.

5. Conclusion

Product branding of product, certain areas, destinations and entire national economies, adds value and provides a guarantee of the quality and value of products. Consumers of tourism products who strive for authenticity and unique experience will visit protected areas and other authentic destinations. Generally, growing visibility can have positive and negative effects. From the aspect of the negative effects, especially regarding the preservation of the environment and the pressures it is exposed to, it is important to ensure sustainable development of destinations. Brand management requires long-term business and strategic orientation towards optimal and ecological development which will benefit both present and future generations.

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